

Mini-Review

Frequency and quantity of milk feeding to dairy calves

Lena Lidfors and Carlos E. Hernandez

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Mini-Review

Frequency and quantity of milk feeding to dairy calves

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1 Executive summary

The EU legislation states that 'All calves must be provided with an appropriate diet adapted to their age, weight and behavioural and physiological needs, to promote good health and welfare.' The Directive also requires that 'All calves must be fed at least twice a day.' (Annex I, 11. and 12.). The Directive does not specify if each meal must contain milk or milk replacer and, if not, at what age a solid meal can be introduced. In some EU farms, calves are fed milk (replacer) only once a day. Calves should be fed an amount of milk equal to 20 % of their birth weight to ensure full growth and vigour. This cannot be drunk in one meal. As long as they are pre-ruminant, calves should thus be fed milk (replacer) at least twice a day. They should receive solid feeds from 2 weeks of age. From 6 weeks of age, they can eat significant amounts of solid feeds and compensate a decrease in milk consumption so that milk (replacer) might be provided once a day only.

2 Foreword

European Reference Centres for Animal Welfare (**EURCAW**) develop and disseminate knowledge and tools to assist the National Competent Authorities (**NCA**) in performing better official controls and enforce EU animal welfare rules.

Council Directive 2008/119/EC of 18 December 2008 that applies to calves up to 6 months of age requires that 'All calves must be provided with an appropriate diet adapted to their age, weight and behavioural and physiological needs, to promote good health and welfare'. To this aim, 'a minimum daily ration of fibrous food must be provided for each calf over two weeks old, the quantity being raised from 50 g to 250 g per day for calves from eight to 20 weeks old.' (Annex I, 11.) The Directive also requires that 'All calves must be fed at least twice a day.' (Annex I, 12.). The Directive does not specify if each meal must contain milk or milk replacer.

The aim of the present document is to review the knowledge about the needs of calves in relation to the frequency of milk meals. The first days of the calves' life, when they should be provided with colostrum, are not covered by the review.

3 Welfare concern

3.1 Background

In some EU regions, it is becoming popular to feed milk (or milk replacer) to calves only once a day (**OAD**) (Gleeson et al., 2008). OAD feeding is when milk (replacer) is fed to calves only once during a 24 h period, with the milk replacer often prepared at a higher concentration (FAWC, 2015). Reasons are that farmers want to reduce labour especially in seasonal grass-based systems. This practice, however, may restrict behavioural and physiological needs of the calf, in particular in calves under 3 weeks of age. It is a potential welfare concern in terms of expression of behaviour, hunger, and health because underfeeding contributes to disease development (FAWC, 2015). To assess if OAD milk feeding can be considered an appropriate diet according to age, we will review the feeding behaviour of calves (based on the literature on suckler calves) and the consequences of the frequency of milk feeding and milk quantities on the welfare of calves. We will analyse when calves are able to obtain the nutrients they need from a solid meal.

3.2 Frequency of milk meals

In calves that are suckled by their dam, suckling frequency and duration depend on many factors, such as age, sex, breed, milk availability, time of the day and feeding motivation (Das et al., 2000; da Costa et al., 2006; de Passillé & Rushen, 2006). With age, the frequency of suckling decreases while the duration of suckling sessions increases. See Wahlin et al. (2021) and Lidfors (2022) for reviews on suckling.

During their first four days of life beef calves (Charolais, Angus, or Hereford) suckle 4–6 times/24 h (Walker, 1950), and during growth 3–5.5 times/24 h (Walker, 1962; Sommerville & Lowman, 1979). Higher frequency of suckling can be observed in calves from more hardy breeds such as Belmont Red, a crossbreed between an indigenous African cattle and a Hereford, or Blue Grey: in Belmont Red, about 9.8 times/24 h at 4 weeks of age and 8.2 times/24 h at 16 weeks of age (Kour et al., 2021) and in Blue Grey, 9.1 times/24 h (Sommerville & Lowman, 1979). A suckling session lasts 7–17 min (Papini et al., 1983; Sommerville & Lowman, 1979). Suckling sessions are short during the first 5 days (7 min on average according to Hogan et al., 2022) and increases thereafter, e.g. 8.3 min at 4 weeks and 9.3 min at 16 weeks of age (Kour et al., 2021). Beef calves can suckle their dam until 10 months of age, as long as the dam produces milk (Veissier et al., 1990).

A similar behaviour is observed in dairy calves that have free access to their dam even when the dam is milked. Dairy calves suckle 4–9 times a day (Fröberg & Lidfors, 2009; Johnsen et al., 2016). The frequency of suckling declines with calf age, e.g. from 6.3 times/24 h at 2 weeks of age to 3.8 times/24 h at 8 weeks of age (Fröberg & Lidfors, 2009) while suckling duration per session increases, e.g., from 6.2 min at 2 weeks of age to 8.8 min at 4 weeks of age (Lidfors et al., 2010). Dairy cows allowed to nurse their calf are generally milked, else their milk production will decrease to cover only the need of the calf.

Up to several months of age, calves therefore suckle several times a day if they are given the opportunity to do so.

3.3 Quantity of milk

Very often, the amount of milk (replacer) fed daily is 10 % of calf's body weight (Heinrichs et al., 2020). OAD milk (replacer) feeding is often done with volumes of 4.5–6 L (approximately 10 % of body weight). Such a volume of milk can be drunk spontaneously in one meal without causing milk to enter the rumen or causing behaviour indicative of abdominal pain (Ellingsen et al., 2016). Calves are able to consume up to 13 % of their body weight in one meal (Ellingsen et al., 2016). Calves with free access to milk however may drink between 10–16 L/day, i.e. over 20 % of their body weight, from 2 to 6 weeks of age (Jasper & Weary, 2002; Borderas et al., 2009). Compared to calves fed milk (replacer) at 20 % body weight in two meals, young calves fed restricted amounts of milk (replacer) have a lower energy balance (with higher blood content in non-esterified fatty acids) and a lower weight gain, they visit the milk feeder more frequently – even if the visit is not rewarded – suggesting that they are hungry (De Paula Vieira et al., 2008), they spend less time in locomotor play but more time in cross-sucking (Jensen et al., 2015; Jongman et al., 2020; Rosenberger et al., 2017; Jung & Lidfors, 2001) and have impaired cognitive performance (Lecorps et al., 2023).

Calves are hormonally primed to digest milk during their first 3 weeks of life (Hammon et al., 2012) and intake of solid feed is negligible up to 3 weeks (Appleby et al., 2001; Borderas et al., 2009). The rumen of calves develops slowly after birth: calves are strictly pre-ruminant for the first 4 weeks of life; thereafter they start eating solid feed and the rumen develops; and from 6 weeks of age they can digest solid feed (Khan et al., 2007). The development of rumen papillae is triggered by the products of microbial fermentations (volatile fatty acids and nitrogen) and the increase in rumen size is triggered by high fiber feeds such as roughage. Large amounts of milk can however limit the consumption of solid feed and thus slow down the development of the rumen (Kahn et al., 2011).

Before 6 weeks of age, calves are unable to compensate for reduced milk intake. From 6 weeks of age, low milk allowances can stimulate calves' intake of concentrates (Jensen et al., 2020) and calves can maintain their growth rate by eating more concentrates when milk allowance is limited (Rosenberger et al., 2016; Figure 1). However, calves should not be considered fully ruminant from 6 weeks of age (Kahn et al., 2015). Dairy calves are often weaned from milk when they are 2 to 3 months of age, provided they have reached a certain target weight and are eating a certain amount of solid feed daily, these targets varying with breed.

Figure 1: Metabolisable energy (Mcal/d) ingested from milk and starter by dairy calves fed 6, 8, 10 or 12 L per day ($n=14$) of whole milk from automatic milk feeders until 6 weeks of age when amount of milk was decreased stepwise until weaning off milk at 50 days of age (adapted from Rosenberger et al., 2016).

3.4 Milk feeding methods

When group housed calves are fed milk from open buckets they consume the milk within 1–2 min and thereafter the occurrence of cross-sucking on other calves increases during up to 20 min (Lidfors, 1993). The pattern of cross-sucking is similar to the suckling pattern on the cow (Lidfors, 1994), which raises the question if artificial milk feeding could be made more similar to a suckling event. Making the delivery of milk through a pipe taking 10 min and feeding milk through floating teats increase time for milk intake and decrease cross-sucking on other calves (Loberg & Lidfors, 2001). Similarly, low milk flow in teat buckets (0.5 vs. 1 L/min) reduces non-nutritive sucking after milk intake, it does however not influence cross-sucking, unless the teat bucket is left so that calves can continue sucking on the dry teat for up to 30 min (Jung & Lidfors, 2001). Nevertheless, a very low flow (300 mL/min in Nielsen et al., 2018) should be avoided because it can limit milk intake.

4 Legal requirements

Council Directive 2008/119/EC of 18 December 2008 requires that 'All calves must be provided with an appropriate diet adapted to their age, weight and behavioural and physiological needs, to promote good health and welfare'. To this aim, 'a minimum daily ration of fibrous food must be provided for each calf over two weeks old, the quantity being raised from 50 g to 250 g per day for calves from eight to 20 weeks old.' (Annex I, 11.) It also requires that 'All calves must be fed at least twice a day.' (Annex I, 12.)

5 Recommendations on calf feeding

Based on scientific evidence, pre-ruminant calves should receive milk quantities per day equivalent to 20 % of their birth weight, divided into at least 2 milk feedings per day and be given sufficient time to ingest their milk (e.g., from teat buckets). The volume of milk (replacer) that can be fed through OAD feeding is unlikely to satisfy calves' behavioural and nutritional needs because they cannot compensate for low milk intake by concentrate consumption. From 6 weeks of age, calves can digest solid feed so that they can receive milk OAD and get another meal of solid feed, on the condition that their rumen is well developed. In addition, the behavioural needs for sucking can be fulfilled by allowing the calves access to an artificial teat in connection to all milk feeding.

6 Recommendations for inspection

To evaluate compliance with the requirement that all calves are provided with an appropriate diet adapted to their age, weight and behavioural and physiological needs information regarding calf feeding routines according to Table 1 must be obtained from the farmer.

If calves get milk (replacer) only once a day during the first weeks of life, they may not be able to drink more than 10 % of their body weight in milk in one occasion. Because calves under 6 weeks of age are not able to compensate for low milk allowance with increased solid feed intake it is expected that this will be reflected in a low weight gain. At 60 days of age calves should weigh twice as they did at birth and from 61 to 120 days of age, they should gain about 1 kg per day (Dairy Calf & Heifer Association, 2022). Because an inspector cannot weigh all calves, checking body condition is the best option (Edmonson et al., 1989, see <https://www.ontario.ca/page/body-condition-scoring-dairy-cattle>). Calves are considered in a low body condition if they obtain Grade 2 or below on a 1–5 body condition scale (Heinrichs & Jones, 2016; see Table 2 for definition).

Underfeeding can also be visible as a dull and dirty coat and a hunched posture. Behaviours of calves that indicate hunger may be observed as a higher incidence of abnormal behaviour, whereas more satiated calves may be observed to either lie down and rest or exploring and playing. A suggested protocol for inspecting whether calves are fed adequately is shown in Table 3.

Table 1: Information on calf feeding routines to be collected on-farm.

Criterion	
Total number of calves	_____
Number of daily meals provided	_____
Milk (replacer)	_____ times per day
Concentrates	_____ times per day
Roughage	_____ times per day
Age at which solid feed is introduced	_____ weeks
Quantity of milk (replacer) fed	
per meal	_____ L \triangleq _____ % of birth weight
per day	_____ L \triangleq _____ % of birth weight

Table 2: Definition of grades 1–5 for body condition score (see <https://www.ontario.ca/page/body-condition-scoring-dairy-cattle>).

Body condition score	Definition
Grade 1 – emaciated	The ends of the short ribs are sharp to the touch and together give a prominent shelf-like appearance to the loin. The individual vertebrae (spinous processes) of the backbone are prominent. The hook and pin bones are sharply defined. The thurl region and thighs are sunken and in-curving. The anal area has receded and the vulva appears prominent.
Grade 2 – thin	The ends of the short ribs can be felt but they and the individual vertebrae are less visibly prominent. The short ribs do not form as obvious an overhang or shelf effect. The hook and pin bones are prominent but the depression of the thurl region between them is less severe. The area around the anus is less sunken and the vulva less prominent.
Grade 3 – average	The short ribs can be felt by applying slight pressure. The overhanging shelflike appearance of these bones is gone. The backbone is a rounded ridge, and hook and pin bones are round and smoothed over. The anal area is filled out but there is no evidence of fat deposit.
Grade 4 – heavy condition	Individual short ribs can be felt only when firm pressure is applied. Together they are rounded over with no shelf effect. The ridge of the back-bone is flattening over the loin and rump areas and rounded over the chine. The hook bones are smoothed over and the span between the hook bones over the backbone is flat. Area around the pin bones is beginning to show patches of fat deposit.
Grade 5 – fat	The bone structure of the topline, hook and pin bones and the short ribs is not visible. Fat deposits around the tailbone and over the ribs are obvious. The thighs curve out, the brisket and flanks are heavy and the chine very round.

Table 3: Points to be inspected to check calves are fed milk adequately. Target grades are shown in green cells. Percentage of calves in each grade is to be recorded. Tolerance values are: body condition, maximum 30 % in grade 2 and 10 % in grade 4, none in grades 1 and 5; coat condition and cleanliness, maximum 15 % in grade 3 and 5 % in grade 2, none in grade 1; body posture, maximum 20 % in grade 3, none in grades 1 and 2; behaviours indicating hunger, maximum 15 % in grade 3 and 5 % in grade 2, none in grade 1.

Measure	Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3	Grade 4	Grade 5
Body condition	Emaciated	Thin	Average	Heavy condition	Fat
Coat condition	Shiny coat	Almost shiny coat	Coat in-between	A bit dull coat	Dull coat
Cleanliness ¹	Very clean	Clean	Some dirt	Dirty	Very dirty
Body posture when standing ²	Being active and attentive	Up-right and moving head	Up-right	Somewhat hunched	Hunched
Behaviours indicating hunger (to be inspected for 30 min)	Lying down	Exploring pen/playing	Standing or displacing other calves	Licking/sucking on pen structures	Cross-sucking on other calves

¹Calves need to be checked for diarrhoea if graded 4–5.

²Calves need to be checked by a veterinarian to rule out underlying diseases if graded 4–5.

7 Conclusion

Dairy calves are often fed restricted amounts of milk (replacer) possibly given in one meal per day. Calves should be fed 20 % of their birth weight in milk, to ensure full growth and vigour. This amount, however, cannot be drunk in one meal. As long as they are pre-ruminant, calves should thus be fed milk (replacer) at least twice a day. They should receive solid feeds from 2 weeks of age. From 6 weeks of age, they can eat significant amounts of solid feeds and compensate a decrease in milk consumption so that milk might be provided in one meal and solid feed in another.

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